

A Synthesis of ($\pm$)-Totaryl Methyl Ether*

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Some quantity of ($\pm$)-totaryl methyl ether (IV) was required in connection with oxidation experiments² in our laboratory and also as a reference compound in cyclodehydration studies^{1,3}. This was synthesised most conveniently by the following procedure.

2-Isopropyl-3-methoxybenzaldehyde¹ was condensed with 2-methylbutan-3-one in presence of alkali. 1-(2-Isopropyl-3-methoxyphenyl)-4-methylpent-1-en-3-one (I), thus obtained, was allowed to react with the methiodide of 1-N-diethylaminopentan-3-one⁴ according to the known procedure⁵ to furnish 2,4,4-trimethyl-3-(2-isopropyl-3-methoxystyryl)cyclohex-2-en-1-one (II). This was reduced successively with hydrogen in presence of palladium-charcoal and lithium aluminium hydride to the cyclohexanol derivative (III) and the latter cyclodehydrated to a stereoisomeric mixture of 14-isopropyl-13-methoxypodocarpa-8,11,13-triene from which ($\pm$)-totaryl methyl ether separated on chromatography in white crystals; m.p. 98-100° in about 50% yield. One other synthesis of this methyl ether is already known⁶.

2-Isopropyl-3-methoxybenzaldehyde was prepared from 2-isopropyl-3-methoxybenzonitrile⁷ by reduction with lithium triethoxyaluminium hydride⁸. The product, b.p. 95-100°/5 mm, which consisted of a mixture of the aldehyde and a little original nitrile, was used directly for subsequent reaction without any further purification.

1-(2-Isopropyl-3-methoxyphenyl)-4-methylpent-1-en-3-one (I).—The above crude aldehyde (15.2 g.), 2-methylbutan-3-one (9 g.), rectified spirit (50 ml), water (12 ml), and 10% aqueous NaOH solution (15 ml) were shaken mechanically for 16 hours. A heavy organic layer separating was taken up in ether and distilled to yield the ketone (I) as a liquid (10 g.), b.p. 135°/4 mm. (Found: C, 77.7; H, 8.9. $C_{16}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 78.0; H, 8.9%). A lower boiling fraction (6 g.) consisting mainly of 2-isopropyl-3-methoxybenzonitrile was recovered. The ketone (I) formed a red DNP.

*This should be regarded as Part V of the Diterpene series.

1. Nasipuri and Pyne, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 4720.
2. *Idem*, *Ind. J. Chem.*, 1963, 1, 227.
3. Nasipuri and Roy, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 327.
4. Adamson *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1376.
5. Church *et al.*, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1960, No. 17, 1; Akter and Weedon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 4059.
6. Taylor, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 3319.
7. Nasipuri and Chaudhuri, *ibid.*, 1958, 2579.
8. Brown *et al.*, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1959, No. 3, 9.

m.p. 175° (from benzene-methanol). (Found: N, 13.5. $C_{22}H_{26}O_3N_4$ requires N, 13.1%).

2,4,4-Trimethyl-3-(2-isopropyl-3-methoxystyryl)cyclohex-2-en-1-one (II).—The foregoing unsaturated ketone (9.5 g.) in dry benzene (25 ml) was added to the methiodide of 1-N-diethylaminopentane-3-one, prepared from the amino ketone (11 g.) and methyl iodide (5 ml). The mixture was cooled and a solution of potassium (5 g.) in ethanol (75 ml) was gradually introduced with vigorous shaking. Next day, it was refluxed on a water bath for 8 hours, ethanol was removed at the water pump, and the residue decomposed with cold 2N- H_2SO_4 . The organic layer was extracted with ether and the extract washed successively with dilute acid and water. The residue after evaporation of the solvent was distilled to yield the unsaturated ketone (II) as a viscous gum (9.5 g.), b.p. 185-90°/3 mm; λ_{max}^{EtOH} 298 μ (ϵ , 16100). It formed a deep red *DNP*, m.p. 183° (from ethyl acetate). (Found: C, 65.9; H, 6.7; N, 11.4. $C_{27}H_{32}O_3N_4$ requires C, 65.9; H, 6.5; N, 11.3%).

2,4,4-Trimethyl-3-(2-isopropyl-3-methoxyphenethyl)cyclohexan-1-one.—The above ketone (6.6 g.) in ethanol (50 ml) was shaken in an atmosphere of hydrogen in presence of 10% palladium charcoal (500 mg.) for 8 hours when two moles of hydrogen were absorbed. The catalyst was filtered and ethanol removed in the pump. The residue was taken up in light petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) and passed through a column of alumina. The ketone was obtained as a crystalline solid, m.p. 85° (from petroleum, b.p. 40-60°). (Found: C, 79.6; H, 10.1. $C_{22}H_{30}O_2$ requires C, 79.7; H, 10.1%). The *DNP* (yellow) formed readily; m.p. 168° (from ethyl acetate). (Found: C, 65.4; H, 7.5; N, 11.6. $C_{27}H_{36}O_3N_4$ requires C, 65.3; H, 7.3; N, 11.3%).

(±)-Totaryl Methyl Ether (IV).—The preceding cyclohexanone (1.7 g.) was reduced with $LiAlH_4$ (0.5 g.) in dry ether (30 ml) to furnish the corresponding cyclohexanol (III) as a gum (1.9 g.). This was taken in a little ether and was added to polyphosphoric acid, prepared from P_2O_5 (31 g.) and 89% H_3PO_4 (20 ml), preheated to 60°. The mixture was stirred at 80-90° for 2 hours and then decomposed with ice. The organic matter was extracted with ether several times, the extract washed successively with dilute alkali and water, and the solvent evaporated. The residue was fractionated by absorption on an alumina column and elution with petroleum (b.p. 40-60°). First few fractions afforded an oil, presumably the β -isomer, and could not be solidified. The later fractions furnished a crystalline product (0.9 g.), m.p. 98-100° (from methanol-ether). (Found: C, 83.8; H, 10.8. $C_{21}H_{30}O$ requires C, 84.0; H, 10.7%). λ_{max}^{EtOH} 284 μ ($\log \epsilon$, 3.21); λ_{min} 249 μ ($\log \epsilon$, 2.39). It did not depress the melting point of an authentic specimen of (±)-totaryl methyl ether⁶.

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